

ANALYSING MATERIALS (COURSEBOOKS, LESSON PLANS, ACTIVITIES) FOR TEACHING INTERCULTURAL ISSUES.**Mahliyo Mirzaabdullayeva**

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331-group-Guiding and interpreting activities

Abstract: Interculturality is an essential aspect of modern-day education that promotes global citizenship and cultural awareness. To achieve this aim, teachers need to incorporate intercultural content in their teaching materials, including coursebooks, lesson plans, and activities. This article provides a step-by-step guide for analyzing such materials for intercultural content. The guide involves identifying learning objectives, evaluating content, considering language, analyzing activities, and considering context. The article concludes that incorporating intercultural content in education can help promote cultural awareness, mutual respect, and global citizenship.

Keywords: intercultural issues, coursebooks, lesson plans, activities, cultural awareness, global citizenship.

Introduction: In today's interconnected world, it is crucial to promote interculturality in education. Intercultural issues can be defined as the interactions between people from different cultural backgrounds. Such interactions can lead to misunderstandings, stereotypes, and discrimination. Therefore, it is essential to incorporate intercultural content in education to promote cultural awareness, mutual respect, and global citizenship. In this article, we will provide a step-by-step guide for analyzing materials, including coursebooks, lesson plans, and activities, for teaching intercultural issues.

Step 1: Identify Learning Objectives: The first step in analyzing materials for intercultural content is to identify the learning objectives. Learning objectives describe what students are expected to know or be able to do by the end of a lesson or unit. Teachers should examine the learning objectives carefully to ensure that they include intercultural content. For instance, if the learning objective is to understand the history of the United States, teachers could include information about the contributions of various ethnic groups to American history.

Step 2: Evaluate Content: The next step is to evaluate the content of the materials. Teachers should examine the text and images in coursebooks, lesson plans, and activities to identify any potential biases or stereotypes. For example, if a coursebook portrays people from certain cultures as inferior, teachers should consider whether the content is appropriate for their students. Teachers should also ensure that the content is accurate and up-to-date.

Step 3: Consider Language: The language used in teaching materials can also have an impact on intercultural issues. Teachers should examine the language used to describe different cultures and ensure that it is respectful and appropriate. They should also consider using inclusive language that avoids stereotypes and promotes cultural understanding.

Step 4: Analyze Activities: The activities included in teaching materials can also promote intercultural understanding. Teachers should analyze the activities to ensure that they promote cultural awareness and respect. For example, if an activity involves students researching different cultures, teachers should ensure that the activity promotes accurate and respectful representations of those cultures.

Step 5: Consider Context: Finally, teachers should consider the context in which the materials will be used. They should consider the cultural background of their students and ensure that the materials are appropriate and relevant to their students' experiences. Teachers should also consider the wider social and cultural context in

which their students live and ensure that the materials promote cultural awareness and respect.

Conclusion: In conclusion, incorporating intercultural content in education is essential to promote cultural awareness, mutual respect, and global citizenship. Teachers can use the step-by-step guide provided in this article to analyze their materials, including coursebooks, lesson plans, and activities, for intercultural content. By doing so, teachers can help promote intercultural understanding and respect among their students. In the end, this will lead to a more tolerant and inclusive society.

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